

REVIEWING SPORTIVE RECREATION ACTIVITIES OF WORKERS WHO WORKED IN ANKARA GİMAT AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRIAL ZONE

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Abstract:

This study focused on reviewing sportive recreation activities of workers who worked in Ankara GİMAT automobile industrial zone. 235 workers who worked in Ankara GİMAT automobile industrial zone participated in the study that was designed in screening model. As data collection tool, Leisure Constraint Scale –which was developed by Alexandris and Carrol and Turkish adaptation of which was done by Gürbüz and Karaküçük– was used. According to study results, it was identified that workers considered social environment and lack of knowledge as the biggest constraint to leisure activity participation and that subdimension was followed by facilities/services and time subdimensions. Besides, according to analysis results about workers' attitudes towards these six factors that constrained them from recreational activity participation, a significant difference existed in facilities/services and social environment and lack of knowledge subdimensions in terms of different age groups.

Keywords: sportive recreation, leisure time

1. Introduction

Definition of sports can be made differently depending on its physiological, social, educational, leisure, economical, cultural and competition dimensions. Sports is a life style. Sports, which completes and affects this life style, has a meaning to direct human life (Zorba, 2004). Basically, sports is an action that human beings do as a competition and physical activity against gravity or a resistance through movement systems.

Time is defined as a course in which an action or an event has occurred, will occur or occurs (TDK, 2016). Time is a constant and sequential process that continues without

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control of human beings coming from the past to the present time and going to the future (Sabuncuoğlu, 2002).

Leisure is defined as a period of time during which one is absolutely free and independent, gets rid of all obligations or occupations of both his and others'-, becomes willingly involved in activities that he chooses and which he spends away from business and work life (Zorba, 2004). Leisure is a time that one spares for himself and in which he has a chance to use and to choose activities freely when he does not work (Sabuncuğlu, 2002).

Recreation is pursuit of leisure time activities that are precious and valuable, please and delight individuals and are voluntarily done. Recreational activities are consisted of some characteristics that do not require any artificial motivation in order to increase attention, give pleasure and delight by stimulating people's lives, are done with the purpose of self-benefit –rather than success-, rid people of their tensions and unpleasant emotions, produce interpersonal communication and human reactions, lead to different occupations and passions, aim at not being dangerous against but being useful for environment, cause social sensitivity and sharing, keep people who make life meaningful and beautiful away from ambiguity and problems (Akgül, Sarol and Gürbüz, 2009).

Recreation is defined as activities that provide personal satisfaction, are done during a time not spent for work or imperative needs and are voluntarily and willingly done in person or in group during a free and independent time spared for oneself in order to get satisfaction and pleasure (Hacıoğlu, Gökdeniz, Dinç, 2003). Considering the above mentioned characteristics of recreation, physical education and sports constitute one of the most comprehensive, diverse and interesting areas of recreation.

Sports and recreation mutually affect each other. Sports provides an important movement area for meeting people's recreational needs while recreation plays effective roles in disseminating and popularizing sports in society and achieving sportive successes.

Generally, there are two kinds of activities as sportive and recreation activities: one is passive participation as spectator and the other one is active participation as player (Akgül et.al. 2009).

Since early stages in which peoples' needs to occupy leisure time were emphasized, participation in sportive activities as spectators have intensively been continuing. Defined as a reflection of passive participation in sports, being spectator may present some factors that may be considered active. These factors may target at integration, psychological achievement, understanding and feeling of sharing among spectators. Besides; due to the fact that people may engage themselves with sports just because they are allured by some sportive branches to which they are spectators, it is understood that passive participation may sometimes turn out to be encouraging and stimulating for activity participation.

Studies point out that number of people who prefer recreational sportive activities is bigger than that of those people who join other activities. Basic reasons for high ratio

to choose active participation in sportive activities during leisure time are rooted in personal and social aspects of sports. Moreover, active participation in sportive activities is realized thanks to the fact that sportive activities provide easy participation and comfort, address tastes and gives opportunities to fulfill demands of people of all ages and sexes. Sportive activities socialize people, create social unity and integrity and play a crucial role in minimizing or controlling effects of stress disease people often encounter. People may build a strong body thanks to regularly done sportive activities. In order reduce stress reaction; all the systems of body, muscles, heart, hormones, metabolic reactions and sensitivity of central nervous system are important (Zorba, 2004).

When sports are preferred and are regularly done as a recreation activity; coping with stress gets easier. When all types of physical activities or sports are done under recreation concept, it is possible that individuals get psychologically and socially satisfied and pleased from these activities even if there are issues such as competing, winning, challenging and risks as a part of activities themselves.

Studies demonstrate that humans are easily affected by psycho-social stressors owing to immobility -in other words, living slowly- and losses of organic resistance. Thus, it is observed that individuals tend more to do recreational sports that will provide them with sufficient movements in a comfortable setting in their leisure time (Zorba, 2004).

Today, health problems have gone up because of mechanization in daily life and limited level of physical movements and thus physical activities become significant for individuals. Physical activities contribute to individuals' physical and psychological wellbeing positively. Those who understand it participate in physical activities quickly. Doing sports regularly is helpful in integration of individual and society, delivery of life of higher quality and being healthy.

This study focused on reviewing reasons for not using leisure time for sportive activities among workers who worked in Ankara GİMAT automobile industrial zone in light of study findings about their age, level of wealth and challenges in the use of leisure time.

This study is regarded important because it will investigate sportive recreation activities of workers who worked in Ankara GİMAT automobile industrial zone, discover and discuss their barriers to leisure activity participation.

2. Material and Method

2.1 Study Model

This was a study in general screening model that investigated sportive recreation activities of workers who worked in Ankara GİMAT automobile industrial zone. Screening Model is a research approach that aims to describe a situation either as it was before or as it is now. The event, individual or object that is the subject of the study is described as it is in its own conditions. No efforts are made to change or to affect them (Karasar, 2016).

2.2 Study Group

Study group was consisted of workers who worked in Ankara GİMAT automobile industrial zone. Study group was consisted of 235 workers who were randomly selected from 105 garages located in Ankara GİMAT automobile industrial zone. At least two workers were selected from each of 105 garages. Thus workers from each garage were included in the study.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

In the study, to determine barriers to participations' sportive recreation activities Leisure Constraint Scale –which was developed by Alexandris and Carrol and Turkish adaptation of which was done by Gürbüz and Karaküçük (2007) was used. To explore participations' socio demographic characteristics, Information Request Form was employed.

Information Request Form includes 14 questions. Leisure Constraint Scale is composed of 27 items that constrain recreation activity participation and 6 subdimensions. The scale has 4 point Likert type format with the following coding: 1 “Absolutely Insignificant” 2 “Insignificant” 3 “Important” and 4 “Very Important”. Participating workers were requested to mark the item that fit them best. Leisure Constraint Scale is composed of six subdimensions: 1st subdimension (individual psychological) includes 1., 2., 3. and 4. items; 2nd subdimension (lack of knowledge and social environment) 5., 6., 7., 8. and 9. items; 3rd subdimension (facilities/services) 10., 11., 12., 13., 14., 15., 16. and 17. items; 4th subdimension (lack of partners) 18., 19. and 20. items; 5th subdimension (time) 21., 22., 23. and 24. items and 6th subdimension (lack of interest) 25., 26. and 27. items. Cronbach Alpha internal consistency analyses suggested that subdimension consistency coefficient was .79 for lack of knowledge and social environment, .63 for facilities/services, .72 for individual psychological, .82 for lack of partners, .64 for time and .75 for lack of interest. Total Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient was .84.

2.4 Data Analyses

For the statistical assessment of the data, SPSS package program was used. During the analyses of data, descriptive statistics were used in order to discover the degree of exposure to factors that constrained leisure activity participation whereas one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used in order to find whether there was a statistically significant difference in subdimension scores of participators in terms of age groups.

3. Results

Table 1: Distribution of participating workers according to age groups

Age	N	%
17-25	75	31.3
26-35	75	31.3
36-55	85	37.4
Total	235	100

The table above demonstrates age distribution of participant workers. According to findings, 31.3% of the workers belonged to 17-25 age group, 31.3% to 26-35 age group and 37.4% to 36-55 group.

Table 2: Distribution of participating workers according to degree of constraints to leisure activity participation

Degree of constraints to leisure activity participation	N	%
Always	22	9.4
Sometimes	125	64.3
Never	62	26.4
Total	235	100

In the table above, participating workers' degrees of constraints to leisure activity participation were presented. According to the table, it was identified that 9.4% of workers always experienced difficulties participating in leisure activities, 64.3% of them sometimes and 26.4% of them never.

Table 3: Average scores of participating workers according to subdimensions of Leisure Constraint Scale

Subdimension	N	$\bar{X}$	Sd.
Lack of interest	235	2.40	.721
Lack of knowledge and social environment	235	2.81	.705
Time	235	2.74	.659
Individual psychological	235	2.45	.652
Facilities/services	235	2.90	.619
Lack of partners	235	2.83	.533

According to the table above, the lowest average score ($\bar{X}=2.40$) was obtained in lack of knowledge and social environment while the highest average score ($\bar{X}=2.90$) was obtained in facilities/services subdimensions.

Table 4: Comparison of participating workers' average scores in subdimensions of Leisure Constraint Scale in terms of age variable

Subdimensions	Age	N	$\bar{X}$	Sd	F	p	Difference Tukey
Individual psychological	17-25	75	2.51	.65	2.006	.137	
	36-35	75	2.52	.66			
	36-55	85	2.34	.62			
	Total	235	2.45	.65			
Lack of partners	17-25	75	2.90	.53	1.264	.284	
	36-35	75	2.82	.56			
	36-55	85	2.77	.5053			
	Total	235	2.83				
Lack of interest	17-25	75	2.44	.66	2.397	.930	
	36-35	75	2.52	.67			
	36-55	85	2.27	.70			
	Total	235	2.40	.72			

Facilities/services	17-25	75	3.06	.72	5.734	.004	1-2*
	36-35	75	2.91	.49			
	36-55	85	2.57	.57			
	Total	235	2.81	.61			
Social environment / Lack of knowledge and social environment	17-25	75	2.88	.70	8.649	.000	1-2*
	36-35	75	2.76	.60			
	36-55	85	2.58	.72			2-3*
	Total	235	2.74	.70			
Time	17-25	75	2.88	.63	4.250	.150	
	36-35	75	2.76	.63			
	36-55	85	2.58	.67			
	Total	235	2.74	.65			

According to the table above, it was found that there was no statistically significant difference in individual psychological, time, lack of partners and lack of interest subdimensions of Leisure Constraint Scale. Yet, a statistically significant difference existed in average scores of facilities/services according to age groups. In order to find out which age group caused the difference, Tukey HSD multiple comparison test was done and according to test results the difference existed between 35-55 age group ($\bar{X}$ =2.73) and 17-25 age group ($\bar{X}$ =3.06) in terms of facilities/services subdimension. On the other hand, a statistically significant difference was also found in lack of knowledge and social environment subdimension and the difference was caused by 36-55 age group ($\bar{X}$ =2.57) and 17-25 ($\bar{X}$ =3.00) age group and 17-25 ($\bar{X}$ =3.00) and 26-35 ($\bar{X}$ =2.91) age group.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, we aimed at factors that would constrain industrial workers' recreational activity participations. According to analysis results done to determine participants' attitudes towards six factors that constrained their recreational activity participation; there was a significant difference in facilities/services, lack of knowledge and social environment subdimensions in terms of age groups. In the study of Alexandris and Carrroll that investigated frequency of university students' recreational sportive activity participation and factors that constrained their participation, it was reported that there was a meaningful correlation between lack of knowledge and social environment and individuals' motivation level and perception of constraints. The results of the current study concurred with the results of Alexandris and Carrroll. Besides, according to study results of Gratton, it was identified that the most important factor for someone to join recreational participation was "money". "Money" in this study result referred to individuals' financial status for entrance fee of sports facilities, transportation, food and beverages consumed during participation and sports materials. Individuals' recreational activity participation is proportionally correlated with their income level. Since "money" is an important factor for facilities/services subdimension, "money" plays a crucial role in recreation activity participation.

In the study of Çelik (2011), participants told that their biggest barrier to participation in leisure activities was lack of knowledge and social environment. In this sense, our study was in line with this study. The studies of Lakot (2015), Has (2016), Sabancı (2016) and Güler (2017) suggested that participants' biggest barrier to participation in leisure activities was facilities/services. The findings of the current study were contradicted by these study findings.

Of constraints that prevented participants from leisure activity participation; the study of Çelik (2011) found no difference in facilities/services and lack of knowledge and social environment in terms of age variable. The current study concurred with the findings of Çelik (2011) in this sense. As the biggest barrier to leisure activity participation, the studies of Lakot (2015), Güler (2017) Has (2016), Sabancı (2016) and Polat (2017) found no difference in lack of knowledge subdimension in terms of age variable and these studies contradicted our study in this sense. On the other hand; the studies of Sabancı (2016), Güler (2017) and Polat (2017) found facilities/services a barrier to leisure activity participation in terms of age variable. The current study concurred with the findings of these studies.

As a result, it was identified that workers considered lack of knowledge and social environment as the biggest constraint to leisure activity participation and that subdimension was followed by facilities/services and time subdimensions. Additionally a significant difference existed in facilities/services and lack of knowledge and social environment subdimensions in terms of different age groups.

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